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Between the Forest and the Village: the New Social Forms of the Baka's Life in Transition

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¹This article is an excerpt of my Master thesis in Visual Cultural Studies defended at the University of Tromsø in Norway in December 2015 under the supervision of Prof Bjørn Arntsen

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Abstract: *The Baka are part of hunter-gatherers group of central Africa generally called “pygmies”. They are most often presented as an indigenous, monolithic and marginalised entity. After a fieldwork carried out in Nomedjoh village in South-Eastern Cameroon, audiovisual and qualitative data have been collected. The theoretical framework follows the dichotomy between structuralism and constructivism. While the former considers identity as a sum of artefacts identifiable and transmissible from generation to generation, the latter, notably with Fredrik Barth, defines ethnicity as a heterogeneous and dynamic entity that changes according to the time and space. Beyond this controversy, the data from Nomedjoh reveal that the Baka community is characterised by two trends: while one group is longing for the integration into modernity at any cost, the other group stands for the preservation of traditional values. Hence, the Baka are in a process of transition.*

Keywords: *Ethnicity, identity, structuralism, constructivism, transition.*

Introduction

After the Cold War and the fall of the Berlin Wall, the world entered into a new era characterised by the triumph of globalisation. The regional political, economic, social and even cultural institutions of different parts of the globe were announced to be harmonised in a “melting pot” allowing free circulation of goods, services and individuals from one continent to another. Surprisingly, the 21st century is rather marked by fierce rise of extremisms, radicalisms with uncountable death toll and material destruction. Some scholars like Tania Murray Li (2000) term this situation as “a global conjuncture of belonging” whereas Samuel Huntington (1993) speaks of “clash of civilization”. If large scale extremist movements like Boko Haram, the Islamic State (IS) are in the present-days widely mediatised, there are several unnoticed ethnic revival movements taking place in almost every country of the world.

On the other hand, many theories, organisations and movements have appeared to be in favour of globalisation. As Herbie Hancock puts it: *“globalisation means we have to re-examine some of our ideas, and look at ideas from other countries, from other cultures, and open ourselves to them”*. In spite of the diversity of wings and conceptions, pro-globalists share in common the conviction that the integration of the world technologically, economically, politically, socially and culturally will enable mankind to get access to well-being.

In fact, these antagonisms and complementarities between the local and the global, the traditional and the modern can be observed at all levels from the micro society to the global society. It is the case of Nomedjoh village where I carried out my fieldwork for the fulfilment of a Master of Philosophy in Visual Cultural Studies at the Arctic University of Norway under the supervision of Bjørn Arntsen. This article is an excerpt from my Master thesis.

During my fieldwork in Nomedjoh, I noticed that the Baka community of South-Eastern Cameroon which used to be presented as an indigenous, monolithic and marginalised entity, is also concerned by these pro-globalist and anti-globalist phenomena. While one group of the Baka is longing for the integration into modernity at any cost, the other group stands for the preservation of traditional values. and his collaborators have opened a new direction to cultural and social anthropology. According to them, culture is not a concrete and immutable thing that a group can possess, but a dynamic way of conceptualizing beliefs, feelings and actions in contact with other individuals or groups. The continual and dynamic process of change is described as follows:

“Culture is now everywhere, under continuous creation – fluid, interconnected, diffusing, interpenetrating, homogenizing, diverging, hegemonizing, resisting, reformulating, creolizing, open rather than closed, partial rather than total, crossing its own boundaries, persisting where we don’t expect it to, and changing where we do” (Sanjek 1991: 622).

According to Frederik Barth, the role of the anthropologist is not to draw a tool bow of the cultural traits of ethnic groups in order to categorise and classify them, but to understand the boundaries, the complexities of ethnic groups in their self-development and in their interaction with other ethnic groups. That’s why he made this assertion which remains as the core of his analysis: it is the “ethnic boundary that defines the group, not the cultural stuff it encloses” (1969:15)

Ethnicity is the product of specific kinds of inter-group relations. An ethnic group cannot exist in isolation, its formation and continuation is dependent upon interaction with ‘Others’ (Barth, 1969). Barth focused on ethnic boundary maintenance, interaction and identity change *across* the boundaries, stating that: categorical ethnic distinctions *do not* depend on an *absence*

of mobility, contact and information, but do entail social processes of exclusion and incorporation whereby discrete categories are maintained despite changing participation and membership in the course of individual life histories.(1969:9-10) Following this perspective, I would like to find out what has changed and what remains while the Baka community is in a process of mobility from the forest to the village and vice versa.

1.1. Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework of this research is uprooted in the debate between the primordialist and the instrumentalist perspectives on ethnicity and its two manifestations: culture and identity.

The constructivist approach as a whole and specifically, Fredrik Barth's theory of ethnicity seem to be very relevant to address the ongoing cleavages and the complexities of the Baka's life between the forest and the village. In fact, Barth and his disciples' perspective emerged in response to structural-functionalist anthropologists. The earlier anthropologists focused on order, integration and stability by defining culture as a coherent, integrated and self-defining entity. In addition, they claimed that ethnicity was synonym of culture and that every ethnic group could be identified and categorised by a certain number of homogeneous and static cultural traits. In other words, the Baka culture would be static and immutable according to them.

However, in the collective book *Ethnic Groups and Boundaries* (1969), Fredrik Barth and his collaborators have opened a new direction to cultural and social anthropology. According to them, culture is not a concrete and immutable thing that a group can possess, but a dynamic way of conceptualizing beliefs, feelings and actions in contact with other individuals or groups. The continual and dynamic process of change is described as follows:

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1. Ethnicity is *not* defined by culture but by social organisation.
2. Ethnic identifications are based on ascription and self-identification. They are situationally dependent and can *change*.
3. The roots of this social organisation are not cultural content but *dichotomization*, so

that the ethnic boundary is a social boundary formed through interaction with ‘Others’. Ethnicity is the product of specific kinds of inter-group relations. An ethnic group

cannot exist in isolation, its formation and continuation is dependent upon interaction with ‘Others’ (Barth, 1969). Barth focused on ethnic boundary maintenance, interaction and identity change *across* the boundaries, stating that: categorical ethnic distinctions *do not* depend on an *absence* of mobility, contact and information, but do entail social processes of exclusion and incorporation whereby discrete categories are maintained despite changing participation and membership in the course of individual life histories. (1969:9-10)

Even as cultural features change and individuals transfer their ethnic membership, the ethnic group continues and is maintained via the “continuing dichotomization between

2. Context of the study

Nomedjoh is a village inhabited predominantly by the Baka. Before delving into a deeper understanding of the dynamics inside and around the village, it is worth giving a glimpse of the history of settlement, socioeconomic conditions as well as its geographic location and cultural diversity.

3.1. The history of Nomedjoh

There are different versions about the history of Nomedjoh. According to the film “Missionary to the Baka” made by Edwin and Paul (2011), the history of Nomedjoh starts in 1973 under the initiative of a young Baka Medjou Medjala. He was a Baka from the clan of Yemakombo who used to live in a village called Nemeyong predominantly inhabited by the Bantu. At that time, the Bantu considered the Baka as servants and even slaves. They used to be sent by the Bantu to hunt or to farm and when their masters were not satisfied; they were publicly beaten sometimes in front of their children and wives. Upset by these inhumane treatments, Medjou Medjala and his family decided to flee and settled in an area 7 kilometres away from his masters. After some months, 9 Baka families from Nemeyong followed him. They found the village full of giant trees locally known as “moabi” (*Baillonella toxisperma*). The 10 families agreed to name the area “Nomedjoh” which means “grove of moabi” or “bosquet de moabi” in French. Since then, different ethnic groups followed in addition to the Baka.

This version of the history of Nomedjoh contradicts the oral source I got. In fact, in an interview with Mboude Merline, she made the following assertion: *“The government and the president took our grand-parents away from the bush and the forest. They brought them here to the village and told them to abandon their lifestyle. They were told to take care of their children, to buy them clothes and to send them to school.”*

However, beyond a simplistic contradiction in the two affirmations, it seems that Mboude Merline referred to the general movement of the Baka who were initially leaving in the Cameroonian rainforests before being transported by the roads (en route) by the colonial and national government respectively.

So whereas the first version talking of the creation of Nomedjoh by a Baka founding father, the second thinks that it is from the initiative of the government. Whatever be the case, the Baka are now settled in Nomedjoh and are living together with other people. Hence, we have the Bamileke, the Bitouri, the Bafia and the Maka who are globally called the “Bantu” and the successive missionaries like Dan Fitzgerald from the United States of America and Ndemmel from Holland.

3.2. Geographic location of the village

Nomedjoh is a village in the Lomié Subdivision, Upper Nyong Division. The Lomié Subdivision has one of the lowest population densities in Cameroon (1.2 persons/km²) and is the last remaining zone of relatively dense forest in the country (Graziani and Burnham 2005).

Nomedjoh is a Baka village with a population of almost 900 individuals, including those in forest camps in the surrounding forest. Women account for 51% of the inhabitants and 59% of the population are young people under the age of 25 (Rob Harley et al. 2010).

At the national level, Nomedjoh is located in the East Region of Cameroon whose main town is Bertoua. When travelling from Bertoua to Yaounde, the capital city of Cameroon, Nomedjoh can be accessed from Abong-Mbang which situated at 112 Km from Bertoua and 265 Km from Yaounde. About 110 Km separate Abong-Mbang to Nomedjoh on an un-tarred rural road which can take around 2 hours 10 minutes drive.

There are three types of houses in Nomedjoh:

- 4 relatively modern habitations made with concrete and cement covered with roofs in zinc. One is the house where the Jean-Paul Ngouffo, the missionary from the Christian Missionary Fellowship International (CMFI) and his family Live. One building where the Church is running a small clinic with limited staff, equipment and pharmaceutical medicines. One hall for the Chapel where the Church holds regular meetings with around 50 members every Tuesday, Friday and Sunday. It is worth mentioning the existence of four houses built in mud bricks and covered with a roof in zinc. The first one is the primary school with around 60 pupils gathered in the same class from class 1 to class 6. Close to it we have the director of the primary school's house. The third one, 200 meters away is used as a bar and the other as house to rent.
- Around 80 houses made in bamboo and mud. The bamboos stand, as plywood, pillars and wall. The rectangular or square wall is covered with mud. The roof is made of bamboos leaves. These are the typical Bantu style building which the Baka are now gradually adopting.
- There are also two huts in Nomedjoh. They are inhabited by two families who couldn't afford the means of constructing houses in the Bantu style (with mud). They are made with small interlaced branches covered with leaves. These were the common Baka housing when they were in the forest. Women were in charge of making them while men were busy with more vigorous tasks like hunting.

3.3. Socioeconomic aspects

The Baka of Nomedjoh are in transition from a livelihood system based predominantly on nomadic hunting and gathering activities towards a more sedentary way of life. This transition

was initiated by colonial settlement policies, and given further impetus by numerous outside interventions and development activities in the community. In the 1970s, Catholic sisters and a Dutch evangelical missionary supported the Baka in their agricultural activities (maize, peanuts, manioc, bananas, coco yam), trained them to make earth dried bricks, and created a school to teach the children French and how to write in the Baka language. As a result the Baka became more integrated into the cash economy in the 1980s, and Baka men began being employed to hunt for bush meat to feed employees in surrounding forestry concessions.

Current livelihood activities include gathering, hunting, fishing, doing work for Bantu in neighbouring villages, making and selling baskets from rattan, selling NTFPs, and agriculture, including some cocoa farming. In addition, there is an increase interest in domestic livestock. In different houses I have noticed the existence of poultry breeding, mixed with goat farming and a community fish farm.

The culture is dualistic, with traditional cultural values and practices coexisting – sometimes uneasily – with new and emergent lifestyle aspects, attitudes and views. A dichotomy in attitudes between young and old places strains on social cohesion. Cash is now given a disproportionate value in Nomedjoh, particularly by men, but experience in managing money is limited and financial management skills are generally weak. In fact, the overall capacity of villagers to organise and manage community-level development projects has historically been very limited.

The primary school with approximately 60 students was an initiative of catholic nuns who later on left the village and the Cameroonian government continued to run it. The director, Minkam Jean made me know that at the beginning of the year they were around 100 pupils but during the course of study, many students desert the school and prefer their traditional hunting gathering activities.

According to Rob Harley, Michael Riddell and Samuel Nnah Ndobe (2010), the socioeconomic characteristics of Nomedjoh can be summarised in the following diagram:

Population	896
Ethnic groups	850 Baka 46 Bantu (Bamileke, Bitouri, Bafia, Maka, Nsimi)
Literacy	Low enrolment rate for children. Primary school and dormitory that houses approximately 20 girls. 25km to Lomié
Distance to nearest town	2011
Approval of community forest	1,942 ha
Area of community forest	Previous illegal logging by encroaching private contractors. No small-scale timber
Status and condition of community forest	extraction by community. Forest is relatively intact and includes high-value species such as Moabi (<i>Baillonella toxisperma</i>).
Main livelihood activities	Gathering Hunting Arable crops (maize, plantain, cassava, and 'jobs' for neighbouring Bantu communities

Wellbeing indicators chosen by community	Artisanal products (mats; baskets) A field that produces enough for 1 the whole family (no hunger in household) 2 Lamp 3 House with thin roof 4 Send children to school Enough pots and kitchen 5 utensils 6 Agricultural material 7 Good clothes A good husband/ wife who is 8 not an alcoholic To have the means available 9 when there is a family problem
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Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of Nomedjoh

Source: Rob Harley, Michael Riddell and Samuel Nnah Ndobe (2010)

From the above diagram, one can understand that the Baka are globally in a state of regeneration where the main goal is not to “change” the nation or the world, but their goals are rather circumscribed at the level of the village. The main needs are the daily existential needs which are to get some food, clothing and to practise agriculture. The futurist aims are for their offspring whom they want to send to school. Basically, the first objective of the majority of Baka, at least according to this diagram, is not to impact on the economy, politics and society at the national or internal level- like the case of the Sami in Northern Norway-. Their first goals are locally oriented.

Though these assertions may give a certain opinion of the Baka community, it is difficult to assume that they are representative of the reality of the whole community. During my stay, I

rather met some Baka with global awareness and the determination to make their voices heard and respected not only in Cameroon but worldwide.

3.4. Local administration and NGOs

Informal institutions dominate decision-making in the village, but there is little experience of strong centralised village leadership. Nomedjoh has been admitted recently as a third degree chieftdom (chefferie de 3e degree) his majesty Ngongo Roger as the chief. He is in charge of small scale administration issue like solving simple conflicts among members.

But the community depends generally on Lomie, the subdivision headquarter where are found the police and decentralised administrative units of the Cameroonian State. Judicially, the forest belongs to the Cameroonian State. That is after the independence, the government has signed exploitation contracts with many logging companies. Some important parts of the forest have been exploited without any fallout for the local communities.

Thanks to the help of NGOs, missionaries and environmental activists, the forest of Nomedjoh has been admitted as a community forest in 2011. This means that the locals are in charge of negotiating exploitation contracts with the logging companies and the funds obtained can be used for the local projects.

The Nomedjoh Community Forest covers a total area of around 1,759 hectares. The terrain is rolling with an altitude that varies between 651 and 718 metres above sea level. The general forest type is mixed evergreen and deciduous humid forest, with a heterogeneous forest structure. Land use within the community forest includes a mix of slash -and-burn agriculture in the agroforestry zone, and hunting, fishing and gathering in the secondary and primary forest.

4. Masters of the forest

The Baka is the only group culturally adapted to the Southeast forest of Cameroon. They are rightly referred to as the "people of the forest". This territory was mainly virgin forest with countless elephants, gorillas and other endangered species. Few other communities, beside them, knew and travelled the deep forest.

The Baka are so much at home in the forest that they were not long ago considered mere "animals" by many Bantu groups. In my desire to understand, feel and experience how their life in the forest was, I followed them in a three day trip in the heart of the deep, thick and luxuriant rainforest of South-Eastern Cameroon. Together, we walked around 40 kilometres away from the village (Nomedjoh) and I seized this opportunity to witness from what is

hunting, gathering, living in symbiosis with the nature is like. This trip gave me the possibility to have some hints in the socioeconomic aspects of the Baka's life in the forest.

4.1. Entering the forest

On the 09th of June 2014, we started our trip to the forest. Before leaving the village in the morning, we sharpened our machetes, prepared a gun, arranged our bags and took some food along with us. It was some raw cassava, matches, salt. We took also torch lamps.

We were a team of 9 men. In fact, the rough conditions in the jungle and its remoteness make it a bit limited for women and children below twelve to go to the forest. The ages varied between 13 and 60 years old with Dieudonne as the eldest and also the leader of the team.

During our trip, I had many discussions with my informants. Dieudonne, Emile and Barthelemy are those with whom I particularly learnt many things about the Baka's life in the forest.

Firstly Ntombombo Dieudonne. He travelled all over the country and gained experience from his different peregrinations. Though he has ever gone to school, now he speaks different languages notably French and Fulfulde (common language in Northern Cameroon). He is a father of two children. His first daughter has just graduated from primary school and was due to continue his studies at the secondary school. In the village, Dieudonne has different responsibilities: religious, politic and social. In fact, he was the first convert of the missionary Jean-Paul Ngouffo and stands as the local pastor of the church. In addition, his role as the president of the Cameroon People's Democratic Movement (CPDM) makes him one of the most influential persons of the village. Moreover, he is the president of the community forest. The forest being the main resource of subsistence, of medicine, of shelter and spiritual life for the Baka, Dieudonne holds the most important department from which the whole village depends. It is with him that I spent most of my time during my fieldwork.

Secondly, Elenga Emile. He is one of the better instructed of the community. He has a driving license and worked for several years with catholic priests and nuns. During his stay in Holland, he attended some lectures about social sciences and got an attestation of attendance.

After having travelled his experience in different cities of the East region, he decided to settle to settle in Nomedjo his village. He presently occupies a temporary position in the clinic as Baka-French interpreter during some meetings that involve people who don't speak Baka.

Father of some 7 children, Emile is considered as one of the intellectuals of the village. He has a driving licence and has worked for several years as the private driver of a catholic priest.

When the priest decided to celebrate his 20 years of pastoral ministry in the Baka community, he travelled with two young men, (among whom Emile) to Holland to show to his fellow citizens live testimony of his work.

Thirdly Malala Barthelemy. Barthelemy is Dieudonne's close neighbour. After some years spent in the South of Cameroon, he went back to the village in order to live with his brothers. He is Dieudonne's assistant in the leadership of the local church. When Dieudonne preaches the gospel in French, Barthelemy interprets in Baka. Barthelemy is also the secretary of the comity for the management of the community forest.

In addition, Barthelemy has started a small income generating activity. He buys handicraft baskets from women in the village and sells them in cities like Abong-Mbang, Yaounde, etc. Thanks to the money gathered, he takes care of his family consisted of his wife and three children.

Apart from the three, Mebo Andre, Ntonga Simon, Djendje Emmanuel, Nkolo Alphone, Mpomo Martial were also in the team with which we went to the forest.

The first day, we spent six hours to walk to the first cabin called Mpam and ran a distance of about 30 Km. This was the record of my life. The name Mpam derives from the name of the closest river to the cabin in the bush. The Baka use rivers as their main reference spots in the forest. On our way, I was appalled by their mastery of the different paths of the deep forest. In fact, I was surprised of the fact despite there was no sign board and no specific road, they were able to know where to walk and not. When walking along forest paths, beneath towering trees, it is almost impossible to see far ahead due to the luxuriant thickness of the undergrowth. Hearing rather than seeing becomes thus the most important sense. The Baka find their way in the forest by "listening to the forest". By recognising the sounds made by different streams of rivers, by distant camps, or even individual trees, and by walking to each other across surprisingly long distances, they are able to know exactly where they are even away from the path. Dhellemmes, a Catholic priest who lived among the Baka for many years noted that, "The intimacy this people has with the forest is so deep and so sacred that at times, it seems wonderful and magic." (1974: 67)

Moreover, the Baka have a very developed smelling capacity. Under the giant trees, it was almost impossible to see the sky and the sun. But since I was used to the northern Norway darkness I was not too annoyed.

After having run around 20 Kilometres, they told me that we are approaching the sacred forest. This is where many rituals and sacrifices are said to be done by the elders. I told them to remind me when we arrive there so that I will film it. Surprisingly, they reminded me only when we passed the sacred forest. I asked them to remind me when we are back. However, at our return, they said we took another way. I didn't understand precisely whether this "omission" was intentional or not.

We finally arrived at Mpam river around 6 PM. We almost ran in order to reach the cabin because rain was about to fall. Dieudonne and Barthelemy even got wet because they took another direction in order to check traps they had previously set.

4.2. Activities in the forest

The 10th of June, the second day, the team was divided in three parts:

- Barthelemy went alone to the former places where they had put traps to catch animals;
- Emile with his gun to go and look for wild boars;
- Dieudonne, the five boys and me went to put new traps.

We walked about 10 Km before finding another cabin. There we spent the whole day putting the traps. All the team was at work. During that period, I was taught how to trap animals in the forest. Dieudonne was particularly very happy for the place because he said it was still virgin. From time to time, he would stop and show me the footsteps of antelopes, wild bears and porcupines though I couldn't differentiate what he was showing me with the other places. When I asked him to tell me how he is able to identify animals' tracks, he told me that knowledge is acquired with time and habit. As he was we were at work, he used to stop and explain me his worry about the gradual destruction of the rainforest. His nostalgia about the times where the forest was totally virgin and animals easy to catch. Now, because of the big engines introduced by the logging companies almost all animals have fled, he would say. His worry was that with the engines there would be no more possibility to find such natural areas where they could hunt. That day, we put 100 traps and stopped when rain started to threaten. We ran back to the first cabin.

In the evening, the team gathered to give an account about what has been done during the day. Emile came back with some honey and mushrooms instead of the wild bear. Barthelemy brought back a tortoise, antelopes and does. In the night, the entire game animal was smoked and the remaining part cooked for our great delight! They told me that they used to get more game that day. Nonetheless, they were very happy of what they got.

On the 11th of June, we got up and Dieudonne lead the team in the morning devotion. Since the game was not as important as usual, Dieudonne wanted us to continue in the forest for the 4th day with the hope to get more. But my drinking water was finished. I proposed them to let Emile accompany me back home. After discussion, they decided to go back to the village together with us. During our way back home, we found more mushrooms and other *Non-timber forest products* (NTFPs) used as spices. We also had the opportunity to harvest honey from a tree. One of the young boys cut a liana and tied it around his waist and the tree. He put an ax on his shoulders and started climbing steps by steps until he reached the place where the bees

were. They were an inoffensive type of bee. So he didn't need fire. With his axe, he succeeded to make a hole which could enable him to remove the honey with his hands. After having extracted the honey he came down.

On our way back home, the team was divided into three groups again. This time, I was with Barthelemy, Dieudonne's close neighbour. We went to visit all the traps they had formerly put in order to see whether some animals had been trapped. Fortunately, one of the traps caught a porcupine. I filmed how Barthelemy killed it. I felt pitiful and scared for that animal. But that is the law of the jungle: either you kill or you are killed.

We arrived in the village in the evening. For me, the trip was full of fragrance and discoveries. I witnessed how the Baka succeeded to keep the rainforest for millennia without destroying it. In fact, they have developed a symbiosis between the nature and their sociocultural activities. Through hunting and gathering, their livelihood in the forest can be termed as "collection economy" contrary to the production economy based on commercialisation and profit making. Furthermore, I experienced a remarkable manifestation of Boudieu's concept of habitus.

According to Bourdieu, habitus is composed of:

"systems of durable, transposable dispositions, structured structures predisposed to function as structuring structures, that is, as principles which generate and organize practices and representations that can be objectively adapted to their outcomes without presupposing a conscious aiming at ends or an express mastery of the operations necessary in order to attain them." (1990:53)

Hence, the knowledge, the practices and the traditions acquired by the Baka in the forest from generation to generation have shaped in them a habitus for the mastery of the life in the forest in spite of the fact that they have now settled in the village or by the road where they were supposed to be assimilated to modern life. That's why I observed that the Baka can be still considered as the "masters of the forest".

6. The new social forms of the Baka's life in Nomedjoh

The interweavement of different the religious, cultural, economic and NGO fields in Nomedjoh is resulting in new configurations, or social forms (Barth,1981) of the Baka's daily life. The following development aims at describing and analysing the incidence of social fields in the practical life. The dynamics among the Baka of Nomedjoh can be understood under the prism of the Barthian constructivism as a conception of ethnicity based on "cultural difference" or what he previously termed as "cultural stuff" (1969). In fact, far than a homogeneous "stuff"

the cultural traits of the inhabitants of Nomedjoh is so diversified that it is impossible to categorize them in a univocal entity.

The previous developments enable me to single out the notion of ethnic identity transformation as the core issue emerging from this work. Social identity refers to how people are defined and regarded in social interactions (Schlenker 1980: 69). The identity that people establish influences their behaviour in front of others, others' treatment of them and the outcomes they receive. Therefore, in their attempts to influence the impressions others form of themselves, a person plays an important role in affecting his social outcomes.

Depending on the position trend to value the cultural and symbolic capital (Emile) or the economic and political capital (Dieudonne), there is an obvious will to present an idealised image of the Baka. This is what Goffman (1952) termed as “self-presentation” or impression management according to Piwinger & Ebert (2001). It is a goal-directed conscious or subconscious process in which people attempt to influence the perceptions of other people about a person, object or event; they do so by regulating and controlling information in social interaction. Following the same perspective, Dieudonne and Emile who can be considered as the “brokers” between the community and the outside world, are trying to convey a new image of the Baka.

6.1. The Baka's life between the forest and the village

The life of the Baka is now divided between the forest and the village. They have been in contact with the Bantu for many generations. In the past, they would only see the Bantu to trade their meat for metal and food. Today, however, the Baka usually build their camp-villages within a few kilometers of the Bantu, where they provide cheap labour for the Bantu's plantations. Change among the Baka intensified in the 1960s, after the independence of Cameroon, with Government programs and with the arrival of the Catholic mission. Roads were fixed and enlarged, which made transportation by vehicle possible for the first in some areas. The government created programs to bring the Baka out of the forest to settle by the road, help them become sedentary and enroll the children in schools. However, their limited budget did not match the task.

Today, the Baka villages are not well developed, as they still spend half of their time in the forest. They do not fully participate in the social structure of the area which includes schools, clinics, markets, and national holidays, and less than 1% are literate. The few children that go to school are the first generation students and are taken out after one or two years to help the adults in the search for food and to care for the younger children. The greatest influence toward

the partial sedentarisation of the Baka was the white Catholic missionaries who designed programs to help create and supervise Baka plantations and teach the people to cultivate in groups.

In Nomedjoh, nearly all families have their own plantations. Some are near the village, while others are as far as seven or forty kilometers away in the forest. Those who stay near the village can easily sell some of their extra food from their crops, but have less access to the forest's goods, such as honey and meat. Most people have two homes, one in their plantation and one in the village.

When away from the village, either in a plantation or on a hunting trip, the Baka live primarily in mongulu (hut or cabin). In the village, their Bantu style mud houses are not as big and strong as the Bantu's houses, but are, however, far bigger and durable than the mongulu.

Today the relationship of Baka with Bantu goes far beyond economics. Friendships and intermarriages are more and more frequent. However, many relationships are painful. Often, in exchange for protection and a few gifts, the Baka provide labor and let the Bantu dominate them. A number of Bantu claim to actually own the Baka of Nomedjoh. They claim superiority and state that the Baka ought to follow their own Bantu traditions, which they consider a better way of life. The Baka do not accept the Bantu's values, especially when it concerns the forest, gender equality, and child raising, but they tolerate the relationship as long as they can benefit materially from it.

Although they make alliances with the Bantu and participate in their social and economic structure, once the relationship is no longer advantageous to them, they may leave for the forest without warning, for an extended period of time. Although they can speak or act like "villagers," they remain as "the people of the forest"

Though the Baka seek unity among themselves while in the forest, in the village they act more independently, like the Bantu. They live two lives, one in the forest and one willingness and not out of obligation. Their way of life is changing rapidly. The prestigious roles of the women who build mongulu (traditional leaf hut) and sing the yéli (rite performed before a hunt) as well as the roles of the elite dancers, singers, and hunters are changing.

Today, few young people can relate to their elders. These young men and women are more and more attracted by the Bantu's possessions, and although they love the forest and find their identity in it, village life by the road is also exciting. On the one hand, in the forest they find tranquility, tradition, and peace with Komba and with one another. On the other hand, in the village they find new excitements and a fast paced life. The Baka are now divided in two different ways and are learning two different lifestyles.

6.2. The transformation of the place of women in Nomedjoh

Ethnic identity development includes self-categorization in, and psychological attachment toward, a biological or blood relation group. Ethnic identity is characterized as part of one's overarching self-consideration. Development of ethnic identity is described as a process of the construction of identity over time, due to a combination of experience and actions of the individual and includes gaining knowledge and understanding of internal dynamics, as well as a sense of belonging to an ethnic group.

Delphine: Farmer and former labourer in Bantou farms

Delphine is Dieudonne's wife (main informant). While she is planting cassava with his son Samuel, she recounts me how she has learnt the practice of agriculture. This know how acquired from the Bantou enabled her to start her private farm thus to depend anymore on them. The presence of Samuel by her sides shows that not only has she learnt agriculture for her personal emancipation but also for her son whom she is initiating to the same technique.

The above examples, though non exhaustive, show how defining the Baka as static, immutable and homogeneous is irrelevant and inapplicable in Nomedjoh. In the face of the limits of the primordialist theory to account for the realities within the ethnic groups of Nomedjoh, I will convene the Barthian perspectives to try to understand the aforementioned dichotomies and complexities.

Globally during my stay in Nomedjoh, I noticed a gradual *division of labour* (Durkheim, 1983) between Baka men and women. In the past the Baka used to move from camp to camp in the forest in the search for food and better environment. Both men, women and children were moving together. But nowadays, women seem to be more confined to domestic chores and income generating activities like making and selling baskets, practising agriculture or selling bush meat and non-timber forest products brought by men from the forest.

For instance, the day we went for hunting in the forest, I was expecting to go with women because I had previously read that they were in charge of making tents and camps in the forest. To my great surprise, no woman joined us. When I asked Dieudonne about this, he replied that most often women no longer go to far hunting place like the one we were to have. They can just go to farms which are close to the village, he added. Hence, the Baka women seem to adopt the new Bantu life by the road where women are considered as key partners in providing income for the family. Following Durkheim's perspective, I can say that the movement of the Baka from the forest to the village is leading them from "mechanic solidarity" to "organic solidarity"

where the men are more in charge of hunting activities (subsistence economy) and the women generally in charge of income generating activities (financial economy) .

6.3. Analysis of some social interactions in Nomedjoh

During my presence in Nomedjoh, I witnessed some events and interactions that enabled me to better understand the ongoing internal dynamics in the community. As recommended by Grønhaug, these social interactions are very important for the operationalisation of anthropological research.

6.3.1. The funeral ceremony

Three weeks before my arrival, there was a Baka grandmother who died in the village.

On the 15-16th of June, I filmed the funeral of an old lady. This was a popular event where all the relatives gathered to pay tribute to the deceased. The ceremony was made up of two parts. One in the night and the other one during the day. Relatives gathered and danced while singing mourning songs. Though any onlooker is free to participate to the dance, it is only those who have been initiated to the “Edjengi” who could perform the main roles and rituals. From a simple rejoicing dance, it gradually escalated into a trance where the performers started to act in an uncontrolled way.

In fact, the “Edjengi” is the spirit in charge of the protection of all the Baka. Some Baka, like Dieudonne refuse his authority and protection. They prefer to be under the protection of Jesus or to be independent from the belief in spirits. But their proportion is very limited compared to the greater number of Baka who are faithful to their traditions and mainly to the “Edjengi”. Since 2004, the pygmies of Cameroon have a 7 day- annual festival called “Libandi”. During that ceremony, one of the main activities is the initiation of their offspring and the profane to the “Edjengi”.

She was aged around 80 years old. Many people testified that she was really lucky to leave that long given the life expectancy in Cameroon which revolves around 55 years. The great number of her children and grandchildren who attended the funeral ceremony supported the fact that she was a kind of “matriarch” for the community of Nomedjoh. After the burial of a Baka, a ceremony is organized in order to send his spirit back to the forest where it will dwell with ejengi and the ancestors. Only those who were faithful and obedient to the ejengi during their life time can deserve this ceremony.

There was one event which particularly stroke my attention. A mixed couple made up of a Bantu (bar tender) and a Baka (woman) was selling liquor and other groceries like salt, matches, tobacco. While the dances are going on more and more frenetic, some men would step out of the dancers and buy some alcohol in order to get more energy and continue to dance

again. I caught even a funny event when a Baka man buy some liquor for one hundred and boast himself in front of a lady who couldn't afford buying.

What was more striking during that event was to see how the Baka where zealous about their tradition whereas the Bantu was preoccupied by making money. Even physically, the couple was different from the other Baka. The man was tall enough and was wearing a hat. As Dieudonne with the Barcelona scarf, wearing a hat was a sign of distinction from the others. Furthermore, the man's wife was wearing a pair of pink trousers. In fact, most of Baka women wear loin (pagne). Just a few, notably the new generation are wearing trousers. Wearing trousers is considered as being a Bantu. It was obvious that the lady had a distance in her behavior with respect to her Baka fellows.

This behavior of some Baka girls who prefer to get married to Bantu men is considered by many Baka men as a betrayal. However they don't express it openly. Publicly and generally, these relationships are accepted. It is mostly in private that they talk of these relations with mistrust. During my exchange with Barthelemy in the forest, he told me:

“Many Bantu men marry our Baka daughters for material interest. They know that the Baka are receiving more and more attention and support from NGOs and the government, they want to benefit from the fallout. “

There is a growing number of mixed marriages (Baka/Bantu) in Nomedjoh. Gaetan married, another Bantu from Bafia near Yaounde, married the chief's daughter. I asked the lady how she was experiencing her marital life. She made me know that she was living in a happy couple. Thanks to her husband, she added, she is now going to school and committed to improve the Baka's living conditions. She continued saying:

“Gaetan taught me many things. With him, I have learnt how to keep my home clean, to speak and to attend important meetings.”

These examples show that there are new dynamics that are being impulse by the mixed marriages in Nomedjoh. These couples can well be considered as “brokers” (Grønhaug) as they introduce new life styles in the community.

7. Conclusion

This research was an attempt to understand how the Baka community of Nomedjoh is coping with or resisting to the local and global changes surrounding them. Two hypothesis were set forth. On the one hand to consider the Baka as a homogeneous and static ethnic group which preserves its identity from generation to generation independently of the influence of the outside world. On the other hand, I was guided by a hypothesis stating that the Baka's identity is transformed by the impact of external factors.

The main contradictions resided on a group which is totally convinced of the necessity to immerse into modern values in order to improve the living conditions of the community.

Contrary to this position, others perceive modernity and its values as a source of devaluation and alienation. They rather fight for the preservation of traditions, customs and beliefs transmitted to them by the ancestors from generation to generation.

The Ejengi is not more considered as the only reference to the Baka's belief but Jesus, or free thinkers who believe to either of them. The forest is not only considered as the sacred and secret aspect of the Baka's identity but also as an instrument that can serve to the improvement of the living conditions of the locals and the development of the region. Hunting and fishing are not the only source of subsistence but agriculture too. The management of forestry resources is not left to the full authority of the State but is gradually transferred to the locals with the help of NGOs. NGOs in their turn are fighting for resilience to global warming and climate change whereas the locals are preoccupied by the daily needs for food, shelter and health.

All these contradictions attest of the fact that the Baka community of Nomedjoh is in constant transformation or in transition. New identities are created based on new experiences and challenges.

Generally, I noticed that the forest is still part of the Baka's bodies and minds. In spite of their settlement by the road, in the village, the Baka are still the "masters of the forest". However, the market economy, bureaucracy and NGOs become an increasingly larger part of their lives. That's why it would be interesting to carry out further studies in the future in order to know how long will the Baka continue to be the "masters of the forest" given that this forest is disappearing.

Hence, it would be difficult to validate the hypothesis according to which they are preserving their identity from generation to generation independently of the influence of the space and time. However, it would be also fallacious to approve completely the assertion stating that the Baka's identity is totally influenced by external factors given that there are still many of them who spare no efforts to perpetuate the ancestral legacy.

As far as I am concerned, I think that the Baka community of Nomedjoh is witnessing both change and resistance, introversion and extroversion to new values. But the question which could be interesting to explore in further studies could be to understand which orientation provide better satisfaction for the locals on the one hand, and on the other hand, how could the Baka manage to satisfy their self-interests without jeopardizing the global climate and the environment.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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